

INTERFACIAL STUDIES OF CELLULOSE WHISKER POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

R. Rusli and S.J. Eichhorn

Materials Science Centre, Northwest Composites Centre and the School of Materials,
Grosvenor Street, University of Manchester, M1 7HS, UK
s.j.eichhorn@manchester.ac.uk

SUMMARY

The molecular deformation of cotton cellulose whisker/epoxy resin (CW/EP) and tunicate whisker/poly(vinyl) acetate (TW/PVAc) composites were investigated using Raman spectroscopy. A shift in the 1095 cm^{-1} Raman peak position is recorded for samples deformed in both tension and compression, which corresponds to the molecular deformation of the cellulose chains within the whiskers. Cyclic molecular deformation tests of the composites provide an insight into understanding the behaviour of these whiskers in the polymer matrix under tension and compression.

Keywords: cellulose whiskers, Raman spectroscopy, deformation, interface studies

INTRODUCTION

Cellulose whiskers are rigid rodlike particles resulting from the acid hydrolysis of cellulose fibres. Cellulose whiskers are produced with the aim of obtaining almost defect free, highly crystalline reinforcement materials and have stiffness near to the theoretical value of cellulose [1]. These whiskers have been produced from a variety of sources such as tunicate [2], cotton [3], bacterial cellulose [4] and microcrystalline cellulose [5]. Cellulose whiskers have high aspect ratios and a large interfacial surface area, although this depends on their origin.

In recent years, many studies have been carried out into polymer nanocomposites by combining various types of these reinforcement materials and polymer matrices. At the same time, the properties of the resulting polymer nanocomposites have also been investigated. Favier and co-workers were the first to study cellulose polymer nanocomposites [6]. The mechanical properties of polymer nanocomposites from tunicate cellulose whiskers and a poly(styrene-butyl acrylate) matrix were reported to be significantly improved due to hydrogen bonding between the cellulose whiskers generating a percolating network [6]. Following this significant finding, many synthetic and natural polymers have been reinforced with cellulose whiskers. However, no reports have been made on the interfacial characterisation of cellulose whiskers-matrix interfaces upon the application of external deformation.

In this study, molecular deformations of CW/EP [7] and TW/PVAc composites were studied using Raman spectroscopy. This was performed by monitoring the shift of the 1095 cm^{-1} Raman peak position associated with the C-O stretching motion of the molecular backbone of the cellulose. [8]

METHODOLOGY

Cotton cellulose whiskers were prepared from sulphuric acid hydrolysis of Whatman filter aid [9]. Epoxy resin beams with dimensions of $80 \times 10 \times 3\text{ mm}^3$ were prepared by mixing Araldite epoxy resin LY5052 and hardener HY5052 in the ratio of 50:19. The cellulose whiskers were dispersed in the hardener of a cold-curing epoxy resin using an ultrasonic bath. The well-dispersed whiskers in hardener was then mixed with the resin and fixed onto the surface of the pre-prepared epoxy resin beams. The samples were left to cure for 7 days at room temperature. A strain gauge was attached to the beam close to the mixture of cellulose whiskers and resin. The sample beams were then tested in 4-point bending under tension and compression.

Tunicate cellulose whiskers were derived from sea tunicates (*Styela clava*) [10]. Sulphate functionalised tunicate whiskers ($\text{SO}_4\text{-TW}$) were prepared by sulphuric acid hydrolysis of cellulose pulp, according to the method described by Favier *et al* [6] with slight modifications. The freeze-dried tunicate whiskers were then dispersed in dimethyl formamide (DMF) at a concentration 5mg/ml . Poly(vinyl) acetate was also dissolved in DMF (5% w/w) before being mixed with the colloidal whiskers suspension. The homogeneous mixture was then solution-casted into Teflon petri dish before the material was compression-moulded in a laboratory press ($90\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at 0 psi for 2 min, followed by an increase of pressure to 3000 psi for 15 min) to yield $200\text{-}300\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thin nanocomposite films. The TW/PVAc composites were incrementally deformed in tension using a customized tensile deformation rig with an attached load cell.

A 785 nm near infrared laser coupled to a Renishaw System 1000 Raman spectrometer, was used to record spectra. All recorded spectra were fitted using a mixed Gaussian/Lorentzian function to determine the peak positions as a function of strain. The laser was polarised parallel to the tensile direction of the samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The 1095 cm^{-1} Raman peak obtained from the cotton whiskers sample shifts towards a lower wavenumber position at a rate of $-0.93\text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ as the strain increases before reaching a plateau value as shown in Figure 1. The data up to the point where they start to plateau are fitted using a linear regression. The gradient of a linear fit to these data is relatively low compared to the previous reported gradients found for tunicate cellulose whisker/epoxy composite ($-2.4\text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$) [11] and bacterial cellulose filaments ($-1.77\text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$) [12]. After 0.65% strain, the presence of a plateau region shows there may be a weakening or a breakdown of the whisker-matrix interface.

After the deformation is released, the data do not follow the same curve as the first loading. This might be due to either the debonding of cellulose whiskers from the matrix or the matrix is yielding. Similar observations are seen for the rest of the cyclic straining.

Figure 1. Molecular deformation of cotton whisker/epoxy resin composite in tension

The cyclic deformation of CW/EP in compression is shown in Figure 2. The increase in the 1095 cm⁻¹ Raman band position could be due to the molecular structure of whiskers in the composite being compressed. However, the increasing compression of cotton whiskers at one point leads to the plateau of data. This might be due to the buckling of the whiskers in the matrix. Hysteresis is observed when the strain in the sample is released and the data are observed not to follow the same curve as the first loading. The rest of the cyclic straining illustrates the same phenomena. The gradients for the linear shifts of the peaks are found to be 0.76 cm⁻¹/% which are much lower, compared to the gradients of cotton cellulose whisker/epoxy composite in tension.

Figure 2. Molecular deformation of cotton whisker/epoxy composite in compression

The shifts in the 1095 cm⁻¹ Raman band for tunicate cellulose whiskers in the composite with tensile deformation are reported in Figure 3. The shifts indicate stress transfer in the composite that occur between the whiskers and the polymer matrix. After a value of about 1.2%, there is a slightly plateau data which could be due to a breakdown of the whisker-matrix interface. A linear fit to these data has a gradient of -1.28 cm⁻¹/% which is higher compared to the CW/EP composite in tension, which indicates the better efficiency in stress transfer from poly(vinyl) acetate matrix to tunicate whiskers.

Figure 3. Molecular deformation of tunicate whisker/poly(vinyl) acetate in tension

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank MOSTI, Malaysia for awarding the scholarship and Professor Derek Gray and Miss Tiffany Abbithol from McGill University, Canada for providing the cellulose whiskers. Thank you also to Professor Stuart Rowan and Dr Christoph Weder from Case Western University, United States for useful discussions and supplies of the tunicate whiskers and TW/PVAc composites.

References

1. Kohler, R. and Nebel, K. (2006) "Cellulose-nanocomposites: Towards high performance composite materials." Macromol. Symp. 244: 97-106
2. Belton, P. S., Tanner, S. F., Cartier, N. and Chanzy, H. (1989) "High-resolution solid-state carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy of tunicin, an animal cellulose." Macromolecules 22(4): 1615-1617
3. Dong, X.M., Revol, J.F. and Gray, D.G. (1998) "Effect of microcrystallite preparation conditions on the formation of colloid crystals of cellulose." Cellulose 5: 19-32
4. Roman, M. and Winter, W.T. (2004) "Effect of sulfate groups from sulfuric acid hydrolysis on the thermal degradation behavior of bacterial cellulose." Biomacromolecules 5(5):1671 -1677
5. Araki, J., Wada, M., Kuga, S. and Okano, T. (1998) "Flow properties of microcrystalline cellulose suspension prepared by acid treatment of native cellulose." Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects 142(1): 75-82
6. Favier, V., Chanzy, H. and Cavaille, J.Y. (1995) "Polymer nanocomposites reinforced by cellulose whiskers." Macromolecules 28: 6365-6367
7. Rusli, R. and Eichhorn, S.J. (2008). "Determination of the stiffness of cellulose nanowhiskers and the fiber-matrix interface in a nanocomposite using Raman spectroscopy." Applied Physics Letters 93(3).
8. Eichhorn, S.J. and Young, R.J. (2001) "The Young's modulus of a microcrystalline cellulose." Cellulose 8:197 -207
9. Gray, D.G. (2008) "Transcrystallization of polypropylene at cellulose nanocrystal surfaces." Cellulose 15: 297-301
10. van der Berg, O., Capadona, J. R. and Weder, C. (2007). "Preparation of homogeneous dispersions of tunicate cellulose whiskers in organic solvents." Biomacromolecules 8(4): 1353-1357.

11. Sturcova, A., Davies, G. R. and Eichhorn, S. J. (2005). "Elastic modulus and stress-transfer properties of tunicate cellulose whiskers." Biomacromolecules 6(2): 1055-1061.
12. Hsieh, Y.C., Yano, H. Nogi, M. and Eichhorn, S.J. (2008) "An estimation of the Young's modulus of bacterial cellulose filaments." Cellulose 15(4): 507-513.